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DESIGN, MEANINGS AND RADICAL INNOVATION: DESIGNING FOR AN INFORMED FUTURE CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses radical innovation, more specifically the design of product meanings, in the context of the tendency of companies to realize increase in sales numbers with the minimum amount of changes in (re) design. Two approaches, i.e. design-driven innovation (Verganti, 2008) and Vision in Product design (Hekkert & Van Dijk, 2010), both explicitly posit product meaning as an important concept in innovation. Based on a comparison of both approaches, we suggest that the focus on meaning in design has the potential of benefitting design companies as well as society. When product meaning is put central in both marketing and design, it is possible to establish successful design agencies that realize meaningful and long lasting products.

Keywords: Product meaning, Radical innovation, Commercial success

Introduction

The Consumer Electronics Show 2011 in Las Vegas had 20,000 new consumer technology products introduced this year. Samsung alone announced 75 'new' products to be launched in 2011.

Helen Waters, New York-based business and design journalist, was baffled by the sudden flooding in the electronics industry and called it a symbol of 'Global Vandalism' (Walters, 2011). 20,000 is indeed a big number. It makes one wonder where we are heading

with this proliferation of products that seem to differ little from each other.

It made us at least think about the philosophy that the industry is trudging on. Are differentiation, real innovation and sustainability in terms of materials, resources and human efforts factors kept in mind when products are designed and developed?

Figure 1: Proliferation of similar products doesn't reflect radical innovation or any change in product meaning.

We doubt the vision behind launching such products that are going to fade out of the market once they haven't received enough attention or reached certain sales target. Next to the question whether we, as civilization, need this deluge of products that seem to provide incremental benefits to our lives, it raises the question whether this business strategy is inevitable for companies to be successful. Intrigued by this apparent conflict, we discuss product meaning as essential component in resolving it. Based on the work of Verganti, we will show that

establishing new product meanings is the essence of real innovation and thereby the road to business success. Based on the work of Hekkert & Van Dijk, we will show that by putting the role of product meaning central within the design process and by enforcing the designer to make this role explicit, the responsibility of the designer is increased. By stating that if you as a designer, want to offer new and unique product meanings to people, the chance of developing products without *raison-d'être* is minimized.

WHAT IS PRODUCT MEANING?

In this section, we probe into what is and what comprises product meaning. Scholars and researchers describe and define product meaning by taking into account a lot of factors. Some approach it through the angle of marketing, others by advertising and some look at it through the lens of human machine interaction. A common agreement about product meaning is that meaning rises in interaction.

Any product, and in fact any 'being' in the world, such as an artifact, animal, plant, or human, is what it is only in relation to people (Heidegger, 1997). Therefore, product meaning can never be regarded as a static property of the product itself. Despite this fact, as we will show, it is possible to design for specific product meanings.

Reflecting on the definitions present in literature, the social context in which people attribute meaning to things is often mentioned.

Domzal and Kernan(1992)explain for instance that the products we consume express who and what we are. Products thereby express cultural codes, like for instance what constitutes youthfulness, sophistication, or middle-class.

In this case, the product becomes a means to relate oneself to others. However, other features of products can be meaningful for people. According to Helfenstein (2005), the concept of product meaning refers to the variety of instrumental and symbolic connotations an individual associates with both tangible and intangible attributes of a particular product or product category.

Products serve psychological functions that embody a person's needs based on his or her utilitarian,

affective and symbolic product values. Allen(2000) adds to this that the relevance of these various aspects is not equal for all people. It is clear that product meaning rises from a variety of product attributes than merely its function.

Allen and Ng's (1997,1999) have developed a product meaning approach that outlines two major sub-systems of the value-attitude-behavior structure that play a role in product preference. It explains that when users evaluate a product's utilitarian meaning they make and attribute by attribute judgement. User values influence the importance of these product's attributes that in turn influence product preference. Or, when users are evaluating a product's symbolic meaning they make an affective, holistic judgment. In this, user human values influence product preference directly. It seems that product meaning derives from an evaluation of the product qualities in relation to user values, which means product meaning is inseparably linked with user values.

In order to design for product meaning, it is important to understand the deepest reasons why people buy products and how products are meaningful to them, i.e., to what values they relate. It is important for companies to look beyond feature, functions and performance and understand the real meaning users give to things. And most of all, it is important for designers to know how to provide people with meaningful designs. Next, we will discuss how product meaning can be positioned within business context, after which the same is done within design context.

DESIGN DRIVEN INNOVATION

In this section, we discuss the design driven innovation approach and how does it intends to integrate design and product meaning for market success.

Innovation is incremental when changes are adding 'more' of a certain quality, i.e, product that are faster or cleaner. Radical Innovation in meaning occurs when new value systems originate that are novel to both producers and users. Verganti (2009) claims that people do not buy products but meanings. People use things for profound emotional,

psychological and sociocultural reasons as utilitarian ones.

The Design driven innovation approach is developed by Roberto Verganti from Politecnico De Milano and stresses the importance of the radical innovation of meaning (2009). This marketing based approach tries to show from a business perspective how the design of product meaning, has a potential to lead to radical innovation and leading market position.

Radical innovations don't provide people with an improved interpretation of what they already know but it proposes a different and unexpected meaning, which is unsolicited and is what people were actually waiting for.

Design driven strategy realizes 'proposals' and 'puts forward a vision'. It is a push strategy which moves against the dominant aesthetic standards and the established product meaning in the industry. The approach focuses on making proposals which will modify the context and building scenarios that would perhaps never occur.

Figure 2: Design driven innovation by Roberto Verganti

As an example, Nokia radically transformed the meaning of mobile phones from connecting offices to 'connecting people'.

People started to see Nokia phones as personal accessories for social relationships rather than devices for business people. A good example of designing new meaning lies in the design of new services. When the services of online banking and car

sharing were introduced, they were completely new or changed the meaning of the existing ones.

Online banking gave quicker, easier and hassle free options for people to manage their finances and car sharing helped them economize on their daily travelling costs apart from being more environment friendly.

Companies that are very successful at design driven innovation base their models on the ideas of elite circles of interpreters or relational assets, or what are called 'key interpreters'. Key interpreters are forward looking researchers or experts who are developing, often for their own purposes, unique visions about how meanings could evolve in the life context which the companies want to investigate. Companies value their interactions with these interpreters as they exchange information on scenarios, test the robustness of their assumptions and discuss their own visions.

There are internal processes through which the firm assesses the knowledge it gains by interacting with the interpreters and then recombines and integrates this knowledge with its own proprietary insight technologies and assets. It tries to reinstate its vision by interpreting this knowledge which further helps in the development of a breakthrough meaning for a product family.

VISION IN PRODUCT DESIGN

To consolidate the vision and context created by the Design Driven Innovation, the designer's process based on the Vision in Product Design approach emphasizes responsibility and sensitivity in design of future products or services.

The context based design approach of Vision in Product Design (ViP), developed by Paul Hekkert and Matthijs van Dijk at the faculty of Industrial Design Engineering at Delft University of Technology is interaction centered and tries to facilitate the generation and design of products that bring new meaning or value to people. This approach takes a designer's perspective and provides hands-on support in how meaning can be given form in design. Hekkert and Van Dijk (2010) state that a product does not have meaning, but that it acquires

meaning. Nevertheless, some qualities are, for various reasons, more easily or univocally attached to products than others. So although Hekkert and Van Dijk agree with Krippendorff (1989) who suggests that ‘no one can presume that form (the designer’s objectified meaning) and (the user’s) meanings are the same’, they believe it is possible to design for product meaning.

ViP is a design approach that focuses on the freedom of the thinking of designers in terms of future visions for products. It also lays emphasis on authenticity of ideas and the responsibility of the designers to create a well-informed future scenario in which design should fit.

As Hekkert and Van Dijk (2011) say, it is crucial to observe people interacting with a product to see the product’s real meaning; in interaction, products reveal meaning and absorb meaning. Interactions with products do not take place in a vacuum. Both products and people are part of, and shaped by, a context. This context can include much more than the momentary, physical environment in which the interaction takes place. The context of any interaction is also composed of social and cultural conditions, laws of (human) nature, economic and

technological changes, etc. In sum, a seemingly endless number of mechanisms or ‘factors’ as called in this approach, co-determine what people are and need, and what products could or should provide. Vision in Product design is a human-centered design method that makes one carefully examine and determine what meaning to offer people in a future world.

Within the process, this meaning should be explicitly defined by means of what they call a ‘design statement’. In formulating this statement designers are asked to literally fill in the dots ‘I want people to...’. Making these explicit addresses the designer’s responsibility for really considering the value of their design. Based on this statement, interaction qualities are defined, from which in its turn the product qualities are derived. In this way the designer is guided in his way down from design goal to product characteristics.

A good example of ViP (Hekkert, 2001) is the development of a lightweight, sustainable concept car for urban areas, the DutchEVO - for a research program by the Delft University of Technology’. The context for this car contains a large number of factors of which three are most important. First, it

Figure 3: The process of ViP as described by Hekkert, P. & Van Dijk, M. 2010, *Vision in Design: A Guidebook for Innovators*.

stressed the principle that the perception of the driver narrows down with increasing speed. Secondly, it was argued that the development of increasing globalization - in culture, economics, religion, etc. - has enhanced our expressive repertoire and resulted in the desire to express ourselves in various ways. Third, because our interaction with our surroundings and other people is more and more mediated by technology, we are starting to hide behind it in order to avoid confrontations.

This context revealed the need for space and freedom to experience our surroundings fully and express ourselves in an unforced manner, so this is what the designers wanted to offer people. This statement was translated into a 'low threshold' concept car, which had a catamaran like structure with excellent aerodynamics allowing the wind to flow under the car without turbulences. It minimally protects one from external climatic agents like wind, temperature, and noise, by using very thin and light materials. The interior of the car is reduced to its bare essentials, thereby avoiding users to process information that is irrelevant or disturbing and allowing them to express themselves freely.

COMPARISON OF VIP AND DDI

We compare VIP and DDI on certain aspects which show the interesting synergies they share or build on. It also shows how they both are strengthening the concept of radical innovation by stressing on transformation of product meaning.

The use of the term 'Product Meaning'

In Hekkert and Van Dijk's book, product meaning is referred to as product qualities that can be attributed to a product by the user, e.g., a product can be 'charming', 'proud', 'stubborn' and so on. In their approach, these product qualities are important to define in order to understand the interaction these qualities will lead to and subsequently the experience they will support. Explicitly defining what it is that you want to offer to people by means of your design, e.g., what you want people to experience, feel, believe etc., is what they call a 'design statement'.

The combination of statement, interaction vision and product qualities, is what Hekkert & Van Dijk call vision. To us, this seems a more detailed version of what Verganti calls product meaning.

The development of future context

An important commonality of both approaches is the envisioning of a future (socio-cultural) context. To be able to realize products that add 'meaning' to the lives of the generations of tomorrow, both marketers and designers need to envision far into the future to guide their directions and choices throughout the process.

Grounding the context

The network of key interpreters enriches the future vision and makes it stronger and diverse in context. According to Verganti (2009), firms survive major sociocultural transitions by continuously refreshing and restructuring their network of interpreters. In ViP, the context is enriched by taking into account the human universals and factors which constitute and guide the designer's statement further into interaction qualities and product qualities.

The use of user research

According to Hekkert et al (2003), the designer empathizes with the future user in his/her world - and various generative tools could be helpful in this respect - but the user is not involved in the design process, as is common practice in design approaches based on user scenarios. In this way, undesirable constraints resulting from user fixations on familiar solution directions are avoided. ViP aims to make these designers aware of and responsible for why and how they do the things they do.

In doing so, both approaches deliberately disregard user-research that is typically revealing people's perceptions of today which is similar to what brand tycoons like Henry Ford and Akio Morita believed too (Neumeier, 2006). Instead, Verganti relies on inputs from a diverse network of interpreters (who are experts in their fields) in order to construct a well-defined and rich future user context. Don Norman (2010) has a similar perspective where he says that fresh eyes can indeed produce insightful

results albeit they must also be educated and knowledgeable.

COMBINATION OF THE TWO TO BENEFIT BOTH BUSINESS & PEOPLE

The development of new product meanings is very important for business success as well as for people. Apart from fulfilling the explicit demands and needs of the users it provides them with a meaningful experience.

The comparison of ViP and DDI approaches suggests that a combination of the two ensures both feasibility (to ensure solid business development) and fit (to prevent useless products) in radical innovation.

Stressing the responsibility for meaningful products
 Design problems are wicked problems, as they deal with a lot of uncertainty and unaccounted hidden factors. Designers tend to define the problem with a holistic approach and formulate the right questions which further leads to solution finding. In ViP (Hekkert 2011), designing is first and foremost the act of defining a vision of what the designer wants to create, not simply creating something in response to a demand. In other words, designing actually starts by establishing the ‘raison d’être’ (the reason for existence) for the final design. ViP was invented for designers who value taking this responsibility.

Stressing the collaboration between key interpreters in establishing the future context to ensure real innovation.

Design Driven Innovation may complement at this stage when expertise of key interpreters could be used to construct a context and future vision which doesn’t depend on the consumer and market research of present world but visualizes and focuses on the needs of tomorrow. The vision created by the internal design lab of the firm and the interpreters is dynamic and helps in design and development of a product/service which is not a mere redesign of what already exists but may disrupt existing and established product meaning .

ViP also emphasizes on responsibility, originality and authenticity of ideas which makes it important for designers as well as marketers and executives to work on lines which aim at efficient management of resources and materials. It would also mean that valuable resources are not wasted in creating gimmicky clones of products to fill up shelf spaces at retailers.

Stressing the longevity of products

One of the significant benefits of design driven innovation is that it generates products with long lives. Design, in particular may have a significant impact on product longevity-for better or worse. According to Verganti(2009), a meaning is not a sum of functions; it is an integrated concept, and it is less sensitive to improvements in specific features. This innovation process works more deeply, on the profound movements underlying the flows and is less sensitive to small movements on the surface. Product longevity saves firms from breakeven fever, generates significant profits, eliminates the need for investments in continuous substitutions, and allows firms to focus their Research and Development budgets in more substantial innovations.

Figure 4: An approach which combines Design Driven Innovation and Vision in Product Design

Fiat Panda was one of the best examples to illustrate product longevity and radical meaning (Verganti,2009). The best metaphor that describes its meaning was a ‘car in sneakers’. And as with sneakers, Panda’s transformability, adaptability and versatility helped it become a social icon that cut across age, gender and social status.

Many incremental innovations simply introduce what design theorist Ezio Manzini(Verganti,2009)calls “semiotic pollution”- a noisy cascade of uncoordinated ideas that simply confuse people. A product designed with a combined approach of Design driven innovation and ViP, would also imply less psychological stress for consumers when they would not need to buy a new product every year to keep themselves updated with the latest technology. A product designed keeping future scenarios in mind would last longer, would reduce the environmental impact in terms of long product lifecycles and disposals or reuse once their life is over.

CONCLUSION

We would like to conclude that product meaning as a concept has an important role to play for radical innovation. A constant focus on meaning in design can definitely result in benefits for businesses as well as users.

Vision in Product design and Design Driven Innovation are approaches that should be practiced to bring about radical changes in design and its meanings. ViP emphasizes on responsible and original design for the users and Design Driven Innovation helps in achieving market or business success. They support the premise that a product should arise of a well informed context and scenario and address valid socio cultural and emotional interactions of the users.

REFERENCES

1. Allen, M. W., & Ng., S. H. (1999). ‘The direct and indirect influences of human values on product ownership’ .*Journal of Economic Psychology*, 20, 5-39.
2. Allen, M. W. (2000). ‘The attribute-mediation and product meaning approaches to the influences of human values on consumer choices’. In F. Columbus (Ed.), *Advances in Psychology Research* (Vol. 1, pp. 31-76).Huntington, NY: Nova Science Publishers.
3. Domzal, T. J., and Kernan,J.B.(1990) "READING ADVERTISING: The What and How of Product Meaning." *The Journal of Consumer Marketing* 9.3
4. Heidegger, M. (1997) *Being and Time: A Translation of Sein und Zeit*, New York University Press, New York (Original Work Published 1926).
5. Helfenstein, S(2005). "Product meaning, affective use evaluation and transfer: A Preliminary study" *An Interdisciplinary Journal on Humans in ICT Environments* Volume 1.1 .
6. Hekkert, P., Snelders, D., Van Wieringen, P. C. W (2003) ‘Most advanced, yet acceptable’: Typicality and novelty as joint predictors of aesthetic preference in industrial design’. *British Journal of Psychology* Volume 94, Issue 1, pages 111-124
7. Hekkert, P. & Van Dijk, M. (2001) ‘ Designing from context: Foundations and Applications of the ViP approach’. In: P. Lloyd and H. Christiaans (Eds.), *Designing in Context: Proceedings of Design Thinking Research Symposium 5*. Delft: DUP Science
8. Hekkert, P. & Van Dijk, M. (2011) *Vision in Design: A Guidebook for Innovators*, BIS Publishers, and Amsterdam.
9. Krippendorff, K. (1989). ‘On the Essential Contexts of Artifacts or on the Proposition That "Design Is Making Sense (Of Things)"'. *Design Issues* _ The MIT Press Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 9-39
10. .Neumeier, M. (2006). *The Brand Gap*. Berkeley (Ca.): New Riders.
11. Norman, D. "Why Design Education Must Change - Core77." *Core77 / Industrial Design Magazine Resource / Home*. Web. 26 Nov 2010.7 Feb 2011
12. Verganti, R. (2008). *Design Driven Innovation: Changing the Rules of Competition by Radically Innovating What Things Mean*. Boston. Harvard Business Press
13. . Verganti, R. (2008). ‘Design, Meanings and Radical Innovation: A Metamodel and a research agenda’. *The Journal of Product Innovation Management*. 25, P 436-456
14. Walters, H (2011). last viewed on 18052011. <http://helenwalters.wordpress.com/2011/01/09/ces-the-perfect-symbol-of-global-vandalism/>